

generative code

Lokalp System

Step 01
Sizing of the initial square unit. During the development of the block, the side length evolved from a minimum of 100 mm to a final dimension of 160 mm.

Step 02
Generation of the initial cubic unit based on the previously generated square.

Step 03
Generation of the hypothesized number of modules defining the block's length. The configuration evolved from 3 length units (Mk I) to a maximum of 6 length units (Mk VI-XII).

Step 04
Definition of the outer dovetail dimensions and upper cutter diameter. The parameterization of these values is essential to allow quick adjustments based on the available cutter diameters.

Step 05
Definition of the internal dovetail side lengths and the lower cutter diameter. The parameterization of these values is essential to enable rapid adjustments based on the available milling tool diameters.

Step 06
Generation of parametrically defined milling cutter tips at the four corners of the trapezoidal recess. The resulting volume serves as the basis for generating the subtractive geometries from the solid block.

Generation of the hourglass-shaped milling profile. The geometry was obtained by mirroring the base trapezoidal module along its shorter horizontal side.

Generation of the hexagonal milling profile. The geometry was obtained by mirroring the base trapezoidal module along its longer horizontal side.

Positioning of the hourglass-shaped milling profile on the relevant faces of the modules. The set of active faces changed several times during the block's development, and from Mk XI onwards, they were no longer perfectly symmetrical.

Boolean subtraction of the hourglass-shaped milling volumes for the generation of the initial lateral notches performed by the dovetail cutter.

Positioning of the hexagonal milling profile on the top and bottom faces of the block. Introduced in Mk IV, this notch frequently changed position during development, shifting by half or a quarter of a block.

Boolean subtraction of the hexagonal milling volumes for the generation of the upper and lower notches created by the dovetail cutter.

Generation of cylindrical milling profiles along the external vertices of the hexagons. These are necessary for the proper insertion of certain biscuits.

Boolean subtraction of the cylindrical milling volumes for the final generation of the LokAlp block.

Boolean subtraction of half the block length to generate the LokAlp 'Short' block.

Generation of the hourglass-shaped milling profile on the new side of the LokAlp 'Short' block.

Boolean subtraction of the hourglass-shaped milling volume for the final generation of the LokAlp 'Short' block.

Generation of the six LokAlp biscuits for connecting the different blocks.